

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

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3 Symbiotic microbiota vary with breeding group membership in a highly social joint-nesting bird

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5 **Table S1** Smooth-billed ani trapping data

Mean attempts/ group	Min attempts	Max attempts	Mist net attempts	Nest trap attempts	Mist net success	Nest trap success	Mean nest trap duration (min)	
3.6	1	6	43	15	0.49	0.40	76.8	
Date	Group	Band #	Trap up	Trap end	Process start	Release	Trap type	Trap duration (min)
19-Nov-21	4Way	934-71653	6:15		7:20	8:20	mist net	
19-Nov-21	4Way	934-71633	6:15		7:20	8:20	mist net	
23-Nov-21	4Way	934-71651	na		na	na	mist net	
18-Nov-21	ERF	na	6:00	6:30			mist net	
20-Nov-21	ERF	934-71691	6:15		6:55	7:20	mist net	
20-Nov-21	ERF	934-71647	6:15		6:55	7:20	mist net	
20-Nov-21	ERF	934-71619	6:15		6:55	7:20	mist net	
25-Nov-21	ERF	na	6:15	7:15			mist net	
14-Dec-21	ERF	na	8:00	8:50			nest trap	50
15-Dec-21	ERF	na	7:17	8:32			nest trap	75
15-Oct-21	EastT	934-71674	~5:50		6:35	7:25	mist net	
3-Nov-21	EastT	934-71662	9:00		10:00	10:15	mist net	
3-Nov-21	EastT	934-71668	9:00		10:10	10:23	mist net	
9-Nov-21	EastT	934-71681	6:00		6:30	8:00	mist net	
9-Nov-21	EastT	934-71664	6:00		6:30	8:00	mist net	
25-Nov-21	EastT	na	6:15	7:00			mist net	
2-Nov-21	FarmEnt	934-71677	9:00		10:00	10:15	mist net	
2-Nov-21	FarmEnt	934-71635	9:00		10:15	10:30	mist net	
2-Nov-21	FarmEnt	934-71699	9:00		na	na	mist net	
26-Nov-21	FarmEnt	na	6:48	7:40			mist net	
3-Dec-21	FarmEnt	na	6:15	7:00			mist net	

4-Dec-21	FarmEnt	na	6:30	7:00			mist net	
9-Dec-21	FarmEnt	na	7:45	na			nest trap	na
10-Dec-21	FarmEnt	934-71646	na		7:23	7:46	nest trap	na
9-Dec-21	Home	934-71630	na		7:00	na	mist net	
25-Oct-21	Mango	934-71658	6:00		6:30	7:20	mist net	
1-Nov-21	Mango	934-71638	6:00		6:30	6:45	mist net	
1-Nov-21	Mango	na	9:50	10:00			mist net	
23-Nov-21	Mango	na	7:00	8:00			mist net	
2-Dec-21	Mango	764-01697	7:15	9:00	7:51	8:13	nest trap	105
2-Dec-21	Mango	764-01692	7:15		8:35	8:52	nest trap	
6-Dec-21	Mango	na	7:10	8:10			nest trap	60
9-Nov-21	NWstn	934-71667	6:00		6:30	8:00	mist net	
9-Nov-21	NWstn	764-01789	6:00		6:30	8:00	mist net	
9-Nov-21	NWstn	914-68077	6:00		6:30	8:00	mist net	
27-Nov-21	NWstn	na	7:15	8:20			mist net	
6-Dec-21	NWstn	na	6:26	7:00			nest trap	34
11-Nov-21	NEWT	934-71606	8:37		9:20	10:15	mist net	
11-Nov-21	NEWT	934-71605	8:37		9:20	10:15	mist net	
11-Nov-21	NEWT	934-71693	8:37		9:20	10:15	mist net	
11-Nov-21	NEWT	934-71692	8:37		9:20	10:15	mist net	
12-Oct-21	Pipeforest	na	17:00	17:50			mist net	
7-Nov-21	Pipeforest	na	9:00	10:00			mist net	
13-Nov-21	Pipeforest	na	8:00	8:30			mist net	
23-Nov-21	Pipeforest	934-71695	6:15		7:00	7:15	mist net	
24-Nov-21	Pipeforest	na	6:30	7:30			mist net	
30-Nov-21	Pipeforest	na	na	na			mist net	
17-Nov-21	RGate	na	7:30	8:00			mist net	
8-Dec-21	RGate	934-71666	7:07		7:16	7:31	nest trap	153
8-Dec-21	RGate	934-71634	7:07		7:58	8:28	nest trap	
8-Dec-21	RGate	934-71644	7:07		8:06	8:28	nest trap	
8-Dec-21	RGate	934-71696	7:07		8:39	8:53	nest trap	

8-Dec-21	RGate	934-71682	7:07	9:40	8:58	9:10	nest trap	
24-Nov-21	SCorner	na	6:15	6:55			mist net	
26-Nov-21	SCorner	934-71657	16:14		17:17	17:34	nest trap	80
1-Dec-21	SCorner	934-71626	16:11		16:30	16:53	nest trap	73
1-Dec-21	SCorner	934-71629	16:11		17:09	17:24	nest trap	
7-Dec-21	SCorner	na	6:30	8:00			mist net	
8-Dec-21	SCorner	934-71686	16:05		16:35	16:49	nest trap	90
8-Dec-21	SCorner	934-71672	16:05		17:23	17:35	nest trap	
11-Dec-21	SCorner	na	7:27	8:20			nest trap	53
26-Oct-21	SEnt	934-71641	6:00		6:30	7:00	mist net	
26-Oct-21	SEnt	934-71623	6:00		7:00	7:36	mist net	
29-Oct-21	SEnt	na	6:00	6:30			mist net	
16-Nov-21	SEnt	934-71700	6:00		7:10	na	mist net	
15-Nov-21	SFarm	934-71615	7:10		7:30	8:20	mist net	
15-Nov-21	SFarm	934-71685	7:10		7:30	8:20	mist net	
15-Nov-21	SFarm	934-71683	7:10		7:30	8:20	mist net	
15-Nov-21	SFarm	934-71650	7:10		7:30	8:20	mist net	
25-Nov-21	SFarm	na	8:07	9:45			nest trap	98
4-Dec-21	SFarm	na	8:00	9:28			nest trap	88
8-Dec-21	SFarm	na	11:20	12:00			nest trap	40
13-Oct-21	Tamarind	934-71659	5:50		6:30	7:10	mist net	
13-Oct-21	Tamarind	934-71625	5:50		7:10	7:50	mist net	
18-Nov-21	Tamarind	na	8:12	9:00			mist net	
22-Nov-21	Tamarind	na	16:30	17:00			mist net	
27-Nov-21	Tamarind	na	7:15	8:20			mist net	
22-Dec-21	Tamarind	934-71678	6:40		7:00	7:20	mist net	
14-Dec-21	VPond	934-71655	na		7:28	na	mist net	
13-Nov-21	W4Way	934-71697	6:15		6:35	7:20	mist net	
13-Nov-21	W4Way	934-71690	6:15		6:35	7:20	mist net	
13-Nov-21	W4Way	934-71675	6:15		na	na	mist net	
19-Nov-21	W4Way	na	6:15	6:40			mist net	

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1-Dec-21

W4Way

na

6:30

8:00

mist net

7 **Table S2** Summary of data used in analysis of the body feather and preen gland microbiota of smooth-billed anis including group
8 metadata. NA = no nest found, DP = nest depredated, ABD = nest abandoned, ABD COMP = nest abandoned due to within-group egg
9 competition.

Total birds	Total Feather	Total Gland	Total Paired									
53	51	50	45									
Sample ID	Bird ID	Sample type	Group	Group size	Number samples	Prop. sampled	Trap date	Number obs	First egg	First chick	Nest fate	
X71633F	X71633	Feather	4Way	8	3	0.38	19-Nov-21	24	~10-Nov	DP 27-Nov	DP (eggs)	
X71651F	X71651	Feather	4Way				23-Nov-21					
X71653F	X71653	Feather	4Way				19-Nov-21					
X71633	X71633	Gland	4Way	8	3	0.38	19-Nov-21					
X71651	X71651	Gland	4Way				19-Nov-21					
X71653	X71653	Gland	4Way				19-Nov-21					
X71662F	X71662	Feather	EastT	13	5	0.38	03-Nov-21	51	NA		NA	
X71664F	X71664	Feather	EastT				09-Nov-21					
X71668F3	X71668	Feather	EastT				03-Nov-21					
X71674F	X71674	Feather	EastT				15-Oct-21					
X71681F	X71681	Feather	EastT				09-Nov-21					
X71662	X71662	Gland	EastT	13	5	0.38	03-Nov-21					
X71664	X71664	Gland	EastT				09-Nov-21					
X71668	X71668	Gland	EastT				03-Nov-21					
X71674	X71674	Gland	EastT				15-Oct-21					
X71681	X71681	Gland	EastT				09-Nov-21					
X71619F	X71619	Feather	ERF	9	3	0.33	20-Nov-21	30	13-Nov	14-Dec	Fledged	
X71647F	X71647	Feather	ERF				20-Nov-21					
X71691F	X71691	Feather	ERF				20-Nov-21					
X71619	X71619	Gland	ERF	9	3	0.33	20-Nov-21					

X71647	X71647	Gland	ERF				20-Nov-21				
X71691	X71691	Gland	ERF				20-Nov-21				
X71635F	X71635	Feather	FarmEnt	9	4	0.44	02-Nov-21	20	10-Nov	07-Dec	Fledged
X71646F	X71646	Feather	FarmEnt				10-Dec-21				
X71677F	X71677	Feather	FarmEnt				02-Nov-21				
X71699F	X71699	Feather	FarmEnt				02-Nov-21				
X71635	X71635	Gland	FarmEnt	9	4	0.44	02-Nov-21				
X71646	X71646	Gland	FarmEnt				10-Dec-21				
X71677	X71677	Gland	FarmEnt				02-Nov-21				
X71699	X71699	Gland	FarmEnt				02-Nov-21				
X71630F	X71630	Feather	Home	8	1	0.13	09-Dec-21	13	27-Nov	ABD COMP	
X71630	X71630	Gland	Home	8	1	0.13	09-Dec-21				
X01692F	X01692	Feather	Mango	10	4	0.4	02-Dec-21	32	15-Nov	14-Dec	
X01697F	X01697	Feather	Mango				02-Dec-21				
X71638F	X71638	Feather	Mango				01-Nov-21				
X71658F	X71658	Feather	Mango				25-Oct-21				
X1692	X01692	Gland	Mango	10	4	0.4	02-Dec-21				
X1697	X01697	Gland	Mango				02-Dec-21				
X71638	X71638	Gland	Mango				01-Nov-21				
X71658	X71658	Gland	Mango				25-Oct-21				
X71605F	X71605	Feather	NEWT	14	3	0.21	11-Nov-21	33	NA		
X71692F	X71692	Feather	NEWT				11-Nov-21				
X71693F	X71693	Feather	NEWT				11-Nov-21				
X71605	X71605	Gland	NEWT	14	3	0.21	11-Nov-21				
X71692	X71692	Gland	NEWT				11-Nov-21				
X71693	X71693	Gland	NEWT				11-Nov-21				
X01789F	X01789	Feather	NWstn	7	3	0.43	09-Nov-21	26	15-Nov	ABD COMP	
X68077F	X68077	Feather	NWstn				09-Nov-21				
X71667F	X71667	Feather	NWstn				09-Nov-21				
X1789	X01789	Gland	NWstn	7	3	0.43	09-Nov-21				
X68077	X68077	Gland	NWstn				09-Nov-21				

X71667	X71667	Gland	NWstn				09-Nov-21					
X71695F	X71695	Feather	Pipeforest	9	1	0.11	23-Nov-21	34	~14-Nov	10-Dec	Fledged	
X71695	X71695	Gland	Pipeforest	9	1	0.11	23-Nov-21					
X71364F	X71364	Feather	RGate	12	5	0.42	08-Dec-21	25	10-Nov	06-Dec	DP (chicks)	
X71644F	X71644	Feather	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71666F	X71666	Feather	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71682F	X71682	Feather	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71696F	X71696	Feather	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71634	X71634	Gland	RGate	12	5	0.42	08-Dec-21					
X71644	X71644	Gland	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71666	X71666	Gland	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71682	X71682	Gland	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71696	X71696	Gland	RGate				08-Dec-21					
X71626F	X71626	Feather	SCorner	9	5	0.56	01-Dec-21	26	12-Nov	07-Dec	Fledged	
X71629F	X71629	Feather	SCorner				01-Dec-21					
X71657F	X71657	Feather	SCorner				26-Nov-21					
X71672F	X71672	Feather	SCorner				08-Dec-21					
X71686F	X71686	Feather	SCorner				08-Dec-21					
X71626	X71626	Gland	SCorner	9	5	0.56	01-Dec-21					
X71629	X71629	Gland	SCorner				01-Dec-21					
X71657	X71657	Gland	SCorner				26-Nov-21					
X71672	X71672	Gland	SCorner				08-Dec-21					
X71686	X71686	Gland	SCorner				08-Dec-21					
X71263F	X71263	Feather	SEnt	11	3	0.27	26-Oct-21	25	24-Nov	ABD COMP		
X71641F	X71641	Feather	SEnt				26-Oct-21					
X71700F	X71700	Feather	SEnt				16-Nov-21					
X71623	X71623	Gland	SEnt	11	3	0.27	26-Oct-21					
X71641	X71641	Gland	SEnt				26-Oct-21					
X71700	X71700	Gland	SEnt				16-Nov-21					
X71615F	X71615	Feather	SFarm	6	4	0.67	15-Nov-21	12	~7-Nov	03-Dec	DP (chicks)	
X71650F	X71650	Feather	SFarm				15-Nov-21					

X71683F	X71683	Feather	SFarm				15-Nov-21				
X71685F	X71685	Feather	SFarm				15-Nov-21				
X71615	X71615	Gland	SFarm	6	3	0.5	15-Nov-21				
X71650	X71650	Gland	SFarm				15-Nov-21				
X71683	X71683	Gland	SFarm				15-Nov-21				
X71625F	X71625	Feather	Tamarind	21	3	0.14	13-Oct-21	43	11-Nov	13-Dec	Fledged
X71659F	X71659	Feather	Tamarind				13-Oct-21				
X71678F	X71678	Feather	Tamarind				22-Dec-21				
X71625	X71625	Gland	Tamarind	21	3	0.14	13-Oct-21				
X71659	X71659	Gland	Tamarind				13-Oct-21				
X71678	X71678	Gland	Tamarind				22-Dec-21				
X71655F	X71655	Feather	VPond	6	1	0.17	14-Dec-21	13	~9-Nov	09-Dec	Fledged
X71655	X71655	Gland	VPond	6	1	0.17	14-Dec-21				
X71675F	X71675	Feather	W4Way	4	3	0.75	13-Nov-21	24	13-Nov	10-Dec	Fledged
X71690F	X71690	Feather	W4Way				13-Nov-21				
X71697F	X71697	Feather	W4Way				13-Nov-21				
X71675	X71675	Gland	W4Way	4	3	0.75	13-Nov-21				
X71690	X71690	Gland	W4Way				13-Nov-21				
X71697	X71697	Gland	W4Way				13-Nov-21				

11 **Table S3** Taxonomic assignment of bacterial amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) collected from adult smooth-billed anis.

SV Pass Filt	Kingdom	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus
SV_0	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Staphylococcus
SV_1	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae	Burkholderia
SV_2	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Enterococcaceae	Enterococcus
SV_3	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	NA
SV_4	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter
SV_5	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_6	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Pseudonocardiales	Pseudonocardiaceae	Actinomycetospora
SV_7	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	Pantoea
SV_8	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	Parabacteroides
SV_9	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae	Burkholderia
SV_10	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_11	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichia	Erysipelotrichales	Erysipelotrichaceae	Erysipelatoclostridium
SV_12	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_13	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Curtobacterium
SV_14	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Rothia
SV_15	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	Corynebacterium
SV_17	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	Parabacteroides
SV_18	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Staphylococcus
SV_19	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	Citrobacter
SV_20	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	NA
SV_21	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Staphylococcus
SV_23	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Pseudonocardiales	Pseudonocardiaceae	Actinomycetospora
SV_24	Bacteria	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
SV_25	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingomonas
SV_26	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_27	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	Proteus
SV_29	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Methylobacteriaceae	Methylobacterium
SV_30	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Stenotrophomonas

SV_31	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_32	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas
SV_33	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	NA
SV_34	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingomonas
SV_37	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Brevibacteriaceae	Brevibacterium
SV_38	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	Pantoea
SV_40	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Pseudonocardiales	Pseudonocardaceae	Actinomycetospora
SV_41	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingomonas
SV_42	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Aurantimonadaceae	Aureimonas
SV_43	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Coprococcus_1
SV_44	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichia	Erysipelotrichales	Erysipelotrichaceae	Faecalitalea
SV_46	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae	Pseudomonas
SV_47	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_49	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Staphylococcus
SV_50	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_51	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	NA	NA
SV_52	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Staphylococcaceae	Macroccoccus
SV_53	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter
SV_54	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_55	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingomonas
SV_56	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Negativicutes	Selenomonadales	Acidaminococcaceae	Phascolarctobacterium
SV_57	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_59	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter
SV_64	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Planococcaceae	Lysinibacillus
SV_65	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_67	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Ruminococcaceae	Ruminococcaceae_UCG-008
SV_69	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_70	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Alcaligenaceae	Sutterella
SV_72	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_73	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	Corynebacterium_1
SV_74	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Oceanospirillales	Halomonadaceae	Kushneria

SV_75	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Coprococcus_1
SV_76	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Ruminococcaceae	Flavonifractor
SV_78	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_79	Bacteria	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	Fusobacterium
SV_81	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_82	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Methylobacteriaceae	Methylobacterium
SV_83	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichia	Erysipelotrichales	Erysipelotrichaceae	Turcibacter
SV_84	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Methylobacteriaceae	Methylobacterium
SV_86	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter
SV_87	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_88	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Aeromonadales	Succinivibrionaceae	Anaerobiospirillum
SV_89	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacteriales	Enterobacteriaceae	NA
SV_90	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Blautia
SV_91	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Aurantimonadaceae	Aureimonas
SV_92	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Methylobacteriaceae	Methylobacterium
SV_95	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_97	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnospiraceae_UCG-004
SV_98	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_101	Bacteria	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriia	Fusobacteriales	Fusobacteriaceae	Fusobacterium
SV_102	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_104	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_105	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Acinetobacter
SV_106	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_107	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Rothia
SV_110	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_112	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pasteurellales	Pasteurellaceae	Avibacterium
SV_114	Bacteria	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
SV_117	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	Parabacteroides
SV_119	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_121	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae	Burkholderia
SV_123	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Sphingomonadaceae	Sphingomonas

SV_124	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Neisseriales	Neisseriaceae	NA
SV_125	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Kocuria
SV_126	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Kocuria
SV_127	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Aeromonadales	Succinivibrionaceae	Anaerobiospirillum
SV_129	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae	Micrococcus
SV_130	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_131	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_132	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae	Bacillus
SV_134	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Cardiobacteriales	Cardiobacteriaceae	Suttonella
SV_136	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Streptococcus
SV_137	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_140	Bacteria	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
SV_141	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_148	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_149	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	Corynebacterium_1
SV_151	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Lactococcus
SV_155	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Moraxella
SV_157	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Negativicutes	Selenomonadales	Veillonellaceae	Megamonas
SV_158	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_159	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Methylobacteriaceae	Methylobacterium
SV_160	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodospirillales	Acetobacteraceae	Roseomonas
SV_162	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Neisseriales	Neisseriaceae	Conchiformibius
SV_164	Bacteria	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
SV_165	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	Parabacteroides
SV_166	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_168	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_169	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Peptococcaceae	Peptococcus
SV_170	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Aurantimonadaceae	Aureimonas
SV_171	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Sphingobacteriia	Sphingobacteriales	Sphingobacteriaceae	Mucilaginibacter
SV_172	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Dermabacteraceae	Helcobacillus
SV_173	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides

SV_175	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Desulfovibrionales	Desulfovibrionaceae	Desulfovibrio
SV_176	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Aurantimonadaceae	Aureimonas
SV_177	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae	NA
SV_179	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Negativicutes	Selenomonadales	Veillonellaceae	Megamonas
SV_180	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae	NA
SV_181	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_183	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Rikenellaceae	Rikenellaceae_RC9_gut_group
SV_184	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Oxalobacteraceae	Massilia
SV_185	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichia	Erysipelotrichales	Erysipelotrichaceae	Erysipelotrichaceae_UCG-001
SV_186	Bacteria	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
SV_191	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria	Xanthomonadales	Xanthomonadaceae	Thermomonas
SV_192	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	Amnibacterium
SV_195	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Fusicatenibacter
SV_196	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Flavobacteriia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Bergeyella
SV_198	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Deltaproteobacteria	Myxococcales	Cystobacteraceae	Melittangium
SV_199	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_204	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Flavobacteriia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	NA
SV_205	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Flavobacteriia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae	Riemerella
SV_207	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_208	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Mycobacteriaceae	Mycobacterium
SV_209	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Ruminococcaceae	Flavonifractor
SV_210	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Intrasporangiaceae	Arsenicicoccus
SV_212	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Coprococcus_1
SV_213	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Coriobacteriia	Coriobacteriales	Coriobacteriaceae	Collinsella
SV_215	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Methylobacteriaceae	Methylobacterium
SV_219	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	Lachnoclostridium
SV_220	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Rikenellaceae	Rikenellaceae_RC9_gut_group
SV_221	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Ruminococcaceae	Flavonifractor
SV_223	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_226	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Ruminococcaceae	Anaerofilum
SV_227	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	NA	NA

SV_228	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinomycetales	Actinomycetaceae	NA
SV_229	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	Parabacteroides
SV_230	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_237	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	NA
SV_239	Bacteria	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
SV_240	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_242	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Bartonellaceae	Bartonella
SV_243	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Ruminococcaceae	Subdoligranulum
SV_244	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Sphingomonadales	Ellin6055	NA
SV_245	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Bacilli	Lactobacillales	Streptococcaceae	Lactococcus
SV_247	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Oxalobacteraceae	Massilia
SV_250	Bacteria	Proteobacteria	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodobacterales	Rhodobacteraceae	Paracoccus
SV_253	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Coriobacteriia	Coriobacteriales	Coriobacteriaceae	Olsenella
SV_254	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae	NA
SV_257	Bacteria	Firmicutes	Clostridia	Clostridiales	Lachnospiraceae	NA
SV_258	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Porphyromonadaceae	Parabacteroides
SV_259	Bacteria	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidia	Bacteroidales	Bacteroidaceae	Bacteroides
SV_262	Bacteria	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Nocardiaceae	Williamsia
SV_263	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Corynebacteriaceae		

13 **Table S4** Eigenvalues and percentage of variance explained for the first five principal
 14 components and rotated component matrix for the first two principal components extracted from
 15 PCA analysis of smooth-billed ani microbiota. Taxonomic assignment based on the Bayesian
 16 Ribosomal Database Project for each amplicon sequence variant (ASV) is shown at the level of
 17 phylum and family. For complete taxonomic information see Table S3.

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	Phylum	Family
Eigenvalue	192.1	37.8	29.3	28.1	24		
% variance explained	24.1	4.7	3.7	3.5	3		
SV_0	-0.00954	-0.02895				Firmicutes	Staphylococcaceae
SV_1	-0.00905	-0.04982				Proteobacteria	Burkholderiaceae
SV_2	-0.02103	-0.02415				Firmicutes	Enterococcaceae
SV_3	-0.01735	-0.01286				Proteobacteria	Enterobacteriaceae
SV_4	-0.02086	-0.01427				Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae
SV_5	0.045836	0.049509				Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_6	-0.05127	-0.00575				Actinobacteria	Pseudonocardiaceae
SV_7	-0.03003	-0.0286				Proteobacteria	Enterobacteriaceae
SV_8	0.004216	-0.02899				Bacteroidetes	Porphyromonadaceae
SV_9	-0.03465	-0.02539				Proteobacteria	Burkholderiaceae
SV_10	0.001686	0.038171				Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_11	-0.05667	-0.02424				Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichaceae
SV_12	0.049911	-0.01125				Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_13	-0.03467	-0.01799				Actinobacteria	Microbacteriaceae
SV_14	-0.02996	-0.01896				Actinobacteria	Micrococcaceae
SV_15	-0.02974	-0.0226				Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriaceae
SV_17	0.019893	0.000279				Bacteroidetes	Porphyromonadaceae
SV_18	-0.01607	-0.09098				Firmicutes	Staphylococcaceae
SV_19	-0.03381	0.153125				Proteobacteria	Enterobacteriaceae
SV_20	-0.04757	-0.01246				Proteobacteria	Pseudomonadaceae
SV_21	-0.0061	-0.06055				Firmicutes	Staphylococcaceae
SV_23	-0.12227	0.110822				Actinobacteria	Pseudonocardiaceae
SV_24	-0.07316	0.02011				NA	NA
SV_25	-0.06227	-0.02113				Proteobacteria	Sphingomonadaceae
SV_26	0.076041	-0.04253				Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_27	-0.00323	0.032391				Proteobacteria	Enterobacteriaceae
SV_29	-0.03809	0.003501				Proteobacteria	Methylobacteriaceae
SV_30	0.004804	-0.00604				Proteobacteria	Xanthomonadaceae
SV_31	0.068007	0.091735				Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_32	-0.08523	-0.10503				Proteobacteria	Pseudomonadaceae

SV_33	0.014379	-0.13853	Proteobacteria	Enterobacteriaceae
SV_34	-0.08549	0.054052	Proteobacteria	Sphingomonadaceae
SV_37	-0.03043	-0.03551	Actinobacteria	Brevibacteriaceae
SV_38	-0.05559	0.143402	Proteobacteria	Enterobacteriaceae
SV_40	-0.09865	0.023259	Actinobacteria	Pseudonocardiaceae
SV_41	-0.07117	0.022844	Proteobacteria	Sphingomonadaceae
SV_42	-0.06752	0.032283	Proteobacteria	Aurantimonadaceae
SV_43	0.075826	-0.02864	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_44	0.098942	-0.10622	Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichaceae
SV_46	-0.07825	0.242563	Proteobacteria	Pseudomonadaceae
SV_47	0.090177	0.096884	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_49	-0.00589	-0.00506	Firmicutes	Staphylococcaceae
SV_50	0.06452	-0.01234	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_51	-0.07812	0.048503	Proteobacteria	NA
SV_52	0.02219	-0.06689	Firmicutes	Staphylococcaceae
SV_53	-0.03584	-0.05184	Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae
SV_54	0.098177	0.047763	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_55	-0.09653	0.067365	Proteobacteria	Sphingomonadaceae
SV_56	0.074662	0.100812	Firmicutes	Acidaminococcaceae
SV_57	0.099288	0.049831	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_59	0.030863	-0.05909	Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae
SV_64	-0.03853	-0.02624	Firmicutes	Planococcaceae
SV_65	0.059512	-0.09685	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_67	0.028763	-0.05221	Firmicutes	Ruminococcaceae
SV_69	0.108213	-0.0584	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_70	0.077161	0.023512	Proteobacteria	Alcaligenaceae
SV_72	0.077995	-0.05111	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_73	-0.1228	-0.01305	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriaceae
SV_74	-0.01612	-0.02982	Proteobacteria	Halomonadaceae
SV_75	0.086107	0.014335	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_76	0.079284	-0.01262	Firmicutes	Ruminococcaceae
SV_78	0.085676	-0.05779	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_79	0.119422	-0.02941	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriaceae
SV_81	0.126566	0.021721	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_82	-0.07317	0.036315	Proteobacteria	Methylobacteriaceae
SV_83	-0.06477	0.025996	Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichaceae
SV_84	-0.09791	0.073229	Proteobacteria	Methylobacteriaceae
SV_86	0.000426	-0.02339	Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae
SV_87	0.120359	0.020979	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_88	-0.00659	0.330768	Proteobacteria	Succinivibrionaceae
SV_89	-0.05253	-0.01893	Proteobacteria	Enterobacteriaceae
SV_90	0.088249	-0.01379	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_91	-0.0562	0.169698	Proteobacteria	Aurantimonadaceae

SV_92	-0.0575	0.009358	Proteobacteria	Methylobacteriaceae
SV_95	0.081498	0.014924	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_97	0.067712	0.052265	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_98	0.11517	0.030344	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_101	0.111372	0.151431	Fusobacteria	Fusobacteriaceae
SV_102	0.102673	-0.08828	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_104	0.072057	0.03769	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_105	-0.01655	-0.02237	Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae
SV_106	0.121628	-0.06091	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_107	-0.06456	-0.10403	Actinobacteria	Micrococcaceae
SV_110	0.110641	0.037463	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_112	-0.02409	-0.06616	Proteobacteria	Pasteurellaceae
SV_114	-0.08474	0.084664	NA	NA
SV_117	0.111695	0.036986	Bacteroidetes	Porphyromonadaceae
SV_119	0.073688	0.052437	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_121	-0.03894	-0.17217	Proteobacteria	Burkholderiaceae
SV_123	-0.12264	0.040054	Proteobacteria	Sphingomonadaceae
SV_124	-0.05166	-0.00258	Proteobacteria	Neisseriaceae
SV_125	-0.0071	0.001259	Actinobacteria	Micrococcaceae
SV_126	-0.04247	-0.02036	Actinobacteria	Micrococcaceae
SV_127	0.091202	0.037945	Proteobacteria	Succinivibrionaceae
SV_129	-0.01476	-0.03981	Actinobacteria	Micrococcaceae
SV_130	0.102601	0.030441	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_131	0.133579	0.00177	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_132	-0.03912	-0.08085	Firmicutes	Bacillaceae
SV_134	-0.02551	-0.0534	Proteobacteria	Cardiobacteriaceae
SV_136	-0.05685	0.024263	Firmicutes	Streptococcaceae
SV_137	0.0782	0.006079	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_140	-0.06392	0.154757	NA	NA
SV_141	0.097826	-0.05453	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_148	0.109735	0.139267	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_149	0.020864	-0.18445	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriaceae
SV_151	-0.01573	-0.15354	Firmicutes	Streptococcaceae
SV_155	-0.01011	-0.07334	Proteobacteria	Moraxellaceae
SV_157	0.105258	-0.01537	Firmicutes	Veillonellaceae
SV_158	0.122824	0.0664	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_159	-0.10178	0.074496	Proteobacteria	Methylobacteriaceae
SV_160	-0.10472	0.126455	Proteobacteria	Acetobacteraceae
SV_162	-0.03128	-0.04447	Proteobacteria	Neisseriaceae
SV_164	-0.09724	-0.06451	NA	NA
SV_165	0.076998	0.020935	Bacteroidetes	Porphyromonadaceae
SV_166	0.058888	0.079706	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_168	0.110678	0.108696	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae

SV_169	0.064867	-0.04941	Firmicutes	Peptococcaceae
SV_170	-0.10404	-0.10928	Proteobacteria	Aurantimonadaceae
SV_171	-0.09834	0.007438	Bacteroidetes	Sphingobacteriaceae
SV_172	-0.04205	-0.06343	Actinobacteria	Dermabacteraceae
SV_173	0.113755	0.122005	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_175	0.042221	-0.00949	Proteobacteria	Desulfovibrionaceae
SV_176	-0.11155	-0.03772	Proteobacteria	Aurantimonadaceae
SV_177	-0.04364	-0.11531	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriaceae
SV_179	0.065304	0.191267	Firmicutes	Veillonellaceae
SV_180	-0.09398	0.015017	Firmicutes	Bacillaceae
SV_181	0.063588	-0.09739	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_183	0.139069	-0.01095	Bacteroidetes	Rikenellaceae
SV_184	-0.04708	-0.0253	Proteobacteria	Oxalobacteraceae
SV_185	0.064726	-0.1076	Firmicutes	Erysipelotrichaceae
SV_186	-0.04425	-0.1051	NA	NA
SV_191	-0.08921	0.064551	Proteobacteria	Xanthomonadaceae
SV_192	-0.06161	-0.19233	Actinobacteria	Microbacteriaceae
SV_195	0.113199	0.021142	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_196	-0.0282	-0.01812	Bacteroidetes	Flavobacteriaceae
SV_198	-0.03305	-0.01325	Proteobacteria	Cystobacteraceae
SV_199	0.088443	0.058259	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_204	0.039658	-0.11464	Bacteroidetes	Flavobacteriaceae
SV_205	-0.0509	-0.00681	Bacteroidetes	Flavobacteriaceae
SV_207	0.049762	-0.00652	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_208	-0.09872	0.117825	Actinobacteria	Mycobacteriaceae
SV_209	0.068778	0.06295	Firmicutes	Ruminococcaceae
SV_210	-0.08572	-0.10809	Actinobacteria	Intrasporangiaceae
SV_212	0.104702	0.007186	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_213	0.090049	0.07671	Actinobacteria	Coriobacteriaceae
SV_215	-0.10333	0.045384	Proteobacteria	Methylobacteriaceae
SV_219	0.125038	-0.05293	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_220	0.072068	0.026145	Bacteroidetes	Rikenellaceae
SV_221	0.135129	0.012256	Firmicutes	Ruminococcaceae
SV_223	0.115695	-0.05901	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_226	0.079475	-0.04078	Firmicutes	Ruminococcaceae
SV_227	-0.06262	-0.10533	Firmicutes	NA
SV_228	0.049771	-0.05731	Actinobacteria	Actinomycetaceae
SV_229	0.099623	-0.09234	Bacteroidetes	Porphyromonadaceae
SV_230	0.127513	0.059737	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_237	0.084078	0.038186	Bacteroidetes	Porphyromonadaceae
SV_239	-0.08731	0.090554	NA	NA
SV_240	0.085509	-0.072	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_242	-0.03689	0.027996	Proteobacteria	Bartonellaceae

SV_243	0.056811	0.017672	Firmicutes	Ruminococcaceae
SV_244	-0.11086	0.073696	Proteobacteria	Ellin6055
SV_245	-0.01474	0.003788	Firmicutes	Streptococcaceae
SV_247	-0.06995	0.050463	Proteobacteria	Oxalobacteraceae
SV_250	-0.02465	0.096974	Proteobacteria	Rhodobacteraceae
SV_253	0.087409	0.039236	Actinobacteria	Coriobacteriaceae
SV_254	-0.0968	-0.04747	Actinobacteria	Microbacteriaceae
SV_257	0.115527	-0.00303	Firmicutes	Lachnospiraceae
SV_258	0.107695	-0.02168	Bacteroidetes	Porphyromonadaceae
SV_259	0.121427	0.102524	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidaceae
SV_262	-0.09869	0.079915	Actinobacteria	Nocardiaceae
SV_263	0.003098	-0.08391	Actinobacteria	Corynebacterium_1

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19

20 **Table S5** Results of PERMANOVA using a Bray-Curtis distance matrix to test for differences in
 21 microbiota among smooth-billed ani body regions (body feathers [n = 51], preen gland [n = 50])
 22 and breeding groups while controlling for bird ID to account for birds that were sampled twice
 23 (once per body region).

	df	Sum of squares	Mean sum of squares	F	R ²	P
Body region	1	3.2	3.2	20.4	0.15	<0.0001
Breeding group	15	4.7	0.3	2.0	0.22	<0.0001
Residuals	84	13.0	0.2	—	0.62	—

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25 **Table S6** Results of a linear model testing for differences in Shannon (alpha) diversity of
 26 smooth-billed ani microbiota among breeding groups.

	Estimate	SE	T	P
Intercept	3.98	0.15	26.07	<0.0001
Type (Gland)	0.06	0.07	0.88	0.383
Breeding group				
EastT	-0.31	0.19	-1.64	0.104
ERF	-0.03	0.21	-0.15	0.88
FarmEnt	-0.12	0.20	-0.64	0.527
Home	0.12	0.30	0.40	0.690
Mango	-0.27	0.20	-1.39	0.169
NEWT	0.01	0.21	-0.07	0.946
NWstn	-0.18	0.21	-0.86	0.391
Pipeforest	0.24	0.30	0.79	0.430
RGate	-0.30	0.19	-1.61	0.112
SCorner	-0.23	0.19	-1.24	0.218
SEnt	0.12	0.21	0.55	0.585
SFarm	-0.12	0.20	-0.61	0.547
Tamarind	-0.19	0.21	-0.92	0.360
VPond	0.11	0.30	0.38	0.706
W4Way	-0.11	0.21	-0.53	0.596

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34 **Figure S2** PCA scree plot

35

36 **Figure S3** Microbial taxa that were differentially abundant between body feathers and the preen
 37 gland of smooth-billed anis. Red dots indicate taxa with an effect size ≥ 1 identified using t-tests
 38 while blue points indicate additional taxa with an effect size ≥ 1 identified using a generalized
 39 linear mixed model. Black points indicate taxa that were not differentially abundant between
 40 body regions. Taxa that were elevated in the preen gland have positive median log₂ values
 41 (rab.win.Gland) while taxa elevated in feathers have negative values (rab.win.Feather).